

Carbon dioxide removal obligations of greenhouse gas debtors

Carbon dioxide removal (CDR) is a vital precondition to achieving the Paris Agreement's temperature goal. The IPCC AR6 does not present any 1.5°C pathways without the deployment of scaled CDR. This raises important questions about the "fair" allocation of responsibility for CDR deployment by countries. In this brief, we outline one possible fair allocation scheme to five countries with the highest recent greenhouse gas debt based on distributive justice principles.

Main takeaways:

- Of the countries responsible for around 85% of current global emissions, around half have emitted beyond their "fair share" since 1990, meaning they incurred greenhouse gas debt. Just five countries incurred roughly half of the recent debt since 1990: the US, Canada, Australia, Saudi Arabia, and the United Arab Emirates.
- Looking ahead to 2050 using the equal cumulative per capita (ECPC) allocation, these five countries with the highest recent greenhouse gas debt would not have the right to emit any further. Instead, they need to reduce their emissions and explore ways to achieve net negative emissions.
- Despite this, the five debtors, under their current near and long-term climate targets, are on track to keep emitting, adding to their debt.
- Countries can only manage down their debt through stringent emissions reductions and sustainably scaling up carbon dioxide removals.
- **A fair carbon dioxide removal contribution in line with 1.5°C-consistent pathways for the five debtors would amount to 86 Gt CO₂e removed by 2050, with the US carrying responsibility for the largest proportion.**
- All countries must cut emissions rapidly and deeply and develop more ambitious climate targets as part of their 2025 Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) revisions, to keep 1.5°C within reach.
- While carbon dioxide removal has a role, it should not overshadow the necessity for immediate and substantial emissions reductions.

Climate action is falling short of meeting Paris Agreement goals

Around half of the greenhouse gas emissions since the pre-industrial period have been emitted in the 30 years following 1990, when the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) published its first report¹.

Responsibility for emissions can be represented using different approaches and schemes. In this analysis, we examine countries

accounting for approximately 85% of current global emissions^{2,3} focusing specifically on the five countries with the highest per capita emissions. Based on our methodological choice, we prioritize two overarching principles – responsibility (i.e., recent cumulative emissions) and equality (i.e., the equal right of all individuals to emit) – to analyse these countries' cumulative per capita greenhouse gas emissions between 1990 and 2022. Results show that approximately half of the countries analysed have higher cumulative green-

We would like to thank the CDR-PoEt consortium partners for their inputs and support

house gas emissions than their "fair share", as estimated by the equal cumulative per capita (ECPC⁴) allocation. These countries have incurred greenhouse gas debt. ECPC is one of many schemes that could be applied^{5,6}, and using another scheme might yield somewhat different results^{7,8}. Analysing greenhouse gas debt instead of only CO₂ debt, as is being done elsewhere in the literature^{6,9} introduces additional uncertainties but also allows a more comprehensive discussion of non-CO₂ contributions to temperature outcomes.

This analysis of ECPC greenhouse gas emissions allowance indicates that just five countries incurred roughly half of that recent global debt*, or around 205 Gt CO₂e: the US (161 Gt CO₂e), Canada (16 Gt CO₂e), Australia (12 Gt CO₂e), Saudi Arabia (11 Gt CO₂e), and the United Arab Emirates (5 Gt CO₂e) (see Figure 1).

It is important to note that the division of countries into those that have credit and those that have debt does not mean that the creditors may claim their full credit, as this would put the 1.5°C limit out of reach¹⁰.

Effort-sharing schemes to inform climate targets

While several countries have begun to reduce their emissions,

progress made in global climate action is still not enough to achieve the Paris Agreement goals and keep 1.5°C within reach. Ambitious mitigation is increasingly needed to bridge the gap between the Paris Agreement's temperature goal and projected warming based on current targets. To get on track, global greenhouse gas emissions have to roughly halve by 2030 (relative to 2019 levels) and reach net zero in the second half of the century, with CO₂ emissions to reach net zero earlier, around mid-century.¹

To break global benchmarks down to the regional or national level, effort-sharing schemes based on different moral perspectives⁹ can help inform policymakers about what constitutes "fair" Paris-aligned national commitments. International climate negotiations have long debated fairness and equitable effort-sharing frameworks, recognised in international agreements and environmental law.¹¹ Since the ECPC scheme accounts for equal per capita access to the global emissions space over time, this allows us to assign moral responsibility accordingly for countries exceeding their fair emissions allowance.

Based on the ECPC scheme beginning in 1990, we find that the five highest recent greenhouse gas debtors have already depleted their fair emissions allocation through 2050. As a result, they will face a

Greenhouse gas debts and fair carbon dioxide removal obligations

Unit: Gt CO₂e

	Recent GHG debt (negative)	Projected future debt (negative)	Future GHG emissions	Future fair CDR obligations in 1.5°C pathways
Total	205	46	106	86
USA	161	35	78	68
Canada	16	3	9	7
Australia	12	4	8	5
Saudia Arabia	11	2	7	4
United Arab Emirates	5	2	4	2

Figure 1. Recent greenhouse gas (GHG) debt (1990-2022), projected future debt based on 1.5°C pathways (2023-2050), future GHG emissions estimated from 2030 NDC and 2050 targets (2023-2050), and equitable 1.5°C-aligned CDR obligation (2023-2050) of the five highest recent GHG debtor countries.

future**^{3,12} debt of around 46 Gt CO₂e from 2023 to 2050 over their per capita allocation, in addition to their recent historical debt of 205 Gt CO₂e (Figure 1). We chose the year 2050 as it is the global benchmark for net zero CO₂ in 1.5°C pathways, and the target year for several countries to reach net zero greenhouse gas emissions.

Therefore, when reviewing the actual targets by the five recent debtor countries in their near-term Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and long-term strategies (LTS), we find that over 100 Gt CO₂e would still be emitted (see Figure 1), continuing to contravene global temperature targets.

Carbon dioxide removal as a complement to pay off greenhouse gas debt

Pathways assessed by the IPCC that achieve the Paris Agreement temperature goal and associated emissions benchmarks require both strong emissions reductions and scaled carbon dioxide removal (CDR) deployment.¹³

Our analysis emphasises that the five debtors thus have a moral duty to implement stringent emissions reductions alongside taking

the lead in a significant and sustainable scale-up of CDR in line with 1.5°C pathways. We derive the CDR contribution as a means of both keeping the 1.5°C goal within reach and addressing past and ongoing harm. Based on the recent greenhouse gas debt of the five countries, we find that they would need to collectively deploy around 86 Gt CO₂e of removals between 2023 and 2050, with the US taking the largest share (see Figure 1).

Need for ambitious 2025 revisions of Nationally Determined Contributions

Overall, our approach emphasises the responsibility for recent and future emissions by the five countries with the highest recent greenhouse gas debt, identified through a specific set of assumptions. More sophisticated effort-sharing approaches, such as those that incorporate ability-to-pay principles reflecting benefits gained from past emissions, would yield different results. Various fairness and effort-sharing schemes may result in identifying a different group of countries or regions as primary debtors.

Regardless of the underlying assumptions, however, our findings underscore the need for urgent, deep emissions reductions and scaled-up CDR – while taking sustainability¹⁴ and feasibility concerns of especially large-scale CDR deployment into account. In addition, the provision of financial support in line with the UNFCCC and the Paris Agreement is essential to keep the 1.5°C warming limit within reach¹⁰.

Actioning these goals requires more ambitious climate targets on track to 2030, ambitious 2035 targets as part of the 2025 NDC revisions cycle, and ambitious long-term targets out to 2050.

*GHG credit/debt has been calculated following van den Berg (2019)⁵. It is defined as the GHG emissions per country that exceed a counterfactual equal per capita emission pathway in the period between 1990-2022. Values were computed incorporating recent historical [1990-2022] cumulative emissions and based on the share of the population.

**The ECPC indicator for 2023 to 2050 was calculated using both global CO₂ and non-CO₂ emissions from 1.5°C-consistent pathways available in the Climate Action Tracker (CAT)³ and publicly available data from the World Population Prospects 2024 from the United Nations¹².

About CDR-PoEt (2021 - 2025)

Carbon Dioxide Removals – Policies and Ethics (CDR-PoEt) examines the ethical and equity implications of policy instruments for CDR, based on interdisciplinary research and stakeholder deliberations. The project specifically evaluates the feasibility ('what can we do from an economic, socio-cultural, and institutional perspective?') and the desirability ('what do we want to do?') of CDR policies and methods in their specific contexts, providing a foundation for developing policy recommendations at local, national and international levels.

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IMPRINT

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The authors would like to thank Dr. Luzie Helfmann for valuable discussions and important contributions to the preparation of this briefing.

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Design and graphic: Gernot Kropf / 2025